

MEDICAL SCIENCES

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SUBSTANTIATION OF THE CHOICE OF SURGICAL REHABILITATION METHODS IN GUNSHOT WOUNDS OF THE MAXILLOFACIAL REGION AN EXPERIMENT

Abstract.

An increased number of injury cases caused by firearms in Ukraine makes it important to improve the accuracy and objectivity of forensic medical examinations in this type of injury by using modern research methods. An experiment was conducted to model gunshot and non-gunshot wounds of the maxillofacial region on 36 white laboratory rats of the Wistar line, males, 7 months old, weighing 400-450 g. All animals were maintained on a complete standard diet of the vivarium of the State Institution "Institute of Dentistry and Maxillofacial Surgery of the National Academy of Medical Sciences of Ukraine" in accordance with the "Guidelines for the maintenance and care of animals": Biochemical studies of blood samples from experimental animals revealed that in the group of animals with gunshot wounds after 21 days, the studied inflammatory markers significantly exceeded those of intact animals: elastase activity by 47.9% and malondialdehyde content by 53.8% ($p < 0.02$). This was significantly higher than in the group of animals with a jaw fracture: elastase activity was 30.3% higher ($p < 0.05$), and malondialdehyde content was 40.4% higher ($p < 0.05$). After 28 days, there was an excess of elastase activity in the serum of animals with gunshot wounds by 18.4% (although $p > 0.1$), and the content of malondialdehyde reached the values in the intact group. Thus, the studies show that the reparative processes in gunshot and non-gunshot wounds of the maxillofacial area follow the well-known laws of repair and regeneration with adequate antibiotic therapy. Indicators of the activity of inflammatory markers, primarily elastase, can be used as a diagnostic sign in planning the timing and scope of surgical and reconstructive operations and in the prevention of postoperative complications.

Key words: Modeling of gunshot wounds on laboratory rats, maxillofacial area, histological examination, biochemical studies.

The aim of the work was to improve the effectiveness of surgical rehabilitation in patients with gunshot wounds of the maxillofacial region by improving certain methods of surgical treatment.

Material and methods. An experiment was conducted to model gunshot and non-gunshot wounds of the maxillofacial region on 36 white laboratory rats of the Wistar line, males, 7 months old, weighing 400-450 g. All animals were maintained on a complete standard diet of the vivarium of the State Institution "Institute of Dentistry and Maxillofacial Surgery of the National Academy of Medical Sciences of Ukraine" in accordance with the "Guidelines for the maintenance and care of animals": EU Council Directive of November 24, 1986 (86/609/EEC). When conducting research with experimental animals, we were guided by the "Rules for the Use of Laboratory Experimental Animals" (2006, Annex 4) and the Helsinki Declaration for the Humane Treatment of Animals, as well as Council Directive 2010/63/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of September 22, 2010 on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes.

For the experiment, all animals were divided into three groups:

- control group - intact animals (n=4);
- group 1 – animals with mechanical damage (fracture) of the left upper jaw (n=16);
- group 2 – animals with simulated gunshot damage (gunshot) of the left upper jaw (n=16).

The duration of the experiment was 28 days.

Mechanical injuries (fractures) on laboratory rats of group 1 were inflicted sparingly under thiopental anesthesia 20 mg/kg with standard Liston nippers in the area of the maxillary bone on the left.

Modeling of gunshot wounds on laboratory rats of group 2 was performed under thiopental anesthesia 20 mg/kg in the area of the maxillary bone on the left. The gunshot wound was carried out using a Stalker 3 revolver (MOD.R1-F 4X9 3") for a Flaubert cartridge (Turkey). The bullet diameter is 4 mm; the initial velocity of the bullet is 170 m/s. The shot was made at an angle of 60-70° from a distance of 15-20 cm.

After the experiment, the animals were left untouched, and no drug supportive therapy was prescribed.

Measurements of parameters in the experimental groups were performed in 4 stages, 4 animals from each group at 7, 14, 21, and 28 days [4-8].

Rats were euthanized from the experiment by total bleeding from the heart under thiopental anesthesia (40 mg/kg), which also eliminates stress and pain during euthanasia.

Blood was drawn, and the oral mucosa, upper jaw, pulp, and brain were isolated for biochemical, histological, and electron microscopic studies [1,2,3].

Results of the study and their discussion. Biochemical studies of blood samples from experimental animals revealed that in the group of animals with gunshot wounds after 21 days, the studied inflammatory markers significantly exceeded those of intact animals: elastase activity by 47.9% and malondialdehyde content by 53.8 % ($p < 0.02$). This was significantly higher than in the group of animals with a jaw fracture: elastase activity was 30.3 % higher ($p < 0.05$), and malondialdehyde content was 40.4 % higher ($p < 0.05$). After 28 days, there was an excess of elastase activity in the serum of animals with gunshot wounds by 18.4 % (although $p > 0.1$), and the content of malondialdehyde reached the values in the intact group.

In the biochemical analysis of bone tissue 21 days after gunshot wound, an increased level of acid phosphatase activity was observed in the jaw tissue by 43.6% ($p < 0.05$), which was higher than in group 1 ($p < 0.05$) and after 28 days this indicator corresponded to the norm ($p > 0.4$). The activity of elastase on day 21 in the bone tissue of the jaws was 33.7% higher than normal ($p < 0.05$), and on day 28 it corresponded to normal values ($p > 0.7$). The calcium content in the jaws of rats 21 and 28 days after gunshot wounding was normalized to the level of the intact group. The data obtained indicate more pronounced processes of bone resorption in the jaws of rats after gunshot wounds than

after fracture. In addition, the processes of osteogenesis after gunshot wounds begin a week later than after fractures.

In biochemical studies after 21 and 28 days, in the oral mucosa of the group with gunshot wounds of the upper jaw, the indicators of inflammatory markers such as elastase activity significantly exceeded the norm by 27.5 % and 2.8 % ($p < 0.02-0.05$), respectively, which was 17.5 % and 27% ($p < 0.02-0.05$) higher than in the oral mucosa of rats with fractures. There was a tendency to increase the activity of acid phosphatase on day 21 by 20.0 % ($0.05 < p < 0.1$) compared with intact animals, which was significantly higher by 28.9 % ($p < 0.01$) compared with animals with a jaw fracture. Normalization of this indicator of inflammation in the oral mucosa of rats occurred on day 28 of gunshot trauma ($p > 0.3$; $p > 0.7$).

The urease activity in the oral mucosa of group 2 after 21 and 28 days significantly exceeded that of the control group by 40.6 % and 35.6 % ($p < 0.01$), respectively. There was a tendency to increase the activity of urease by 15.8 % and 13.2 % ($0.05 < p < 0.1$) compared with the level of this indicator in group 1.

Indicators of the antioxidant-prooxidant system in the oral mucosa of rats 21 and 28 days after gunshot wound, such as catalase activity, remained at a significantly low level by 41.2 % and 21.2 % ($p < 0.01-0.02$) compared to the value in the intact group, which was 18.6 % lower ($p < 0.02$) than in the group with a fracture on day 21. At the last stage, after 28 days, the catalase activity in the oral mucosa of rats with gunshot wounds and fracture was the same ($p > 0.25$) (table 1-3).

Table 1

Serum parameters of rats at different times after fracture or gunshot wound in the upper jaw				
Periods	Groups	Elastase activity, μkat	Catalase activity, μka	MDA content, mmol
Intact group		134,20 ± 9,42	0,195±0,010	0,52±0,04
7 days	fracture	225,12±14,36 $p < 0,01$	0,166±0,011 $p > 0,1$	0,76±0,06 $p < 0,05$
	fire	314,97±11,45 $p < 0,001$ $p_1 < 0,01$	0,130±0,010 $p < 0,01$ $0,05 < p_1 < 0,1$	1,18±0,06 $p < 0,001$ $p_1 < 0,01$
14 days	fracture	180,0±13,64 $p < 0,05$	0,172±0,012 $p > 0,1$	0,69±0,08 $p > 0,1$
	fire	253,73±12,48 $p < 0,001$ $p_1 < 0,02$	0,135±0,013 $p < 0,02$ $0,05 < p_1 < 0,1$	0,92±0,08 $p < 0,01$ $0,05 < p_1 < 0,1$
21 days	fracture	152,33±11,51 $p > 0,25$	0,170 ± 0,012 $p > 0,1$	0,57±0,05 $p > 0,4$
	fire	198,53±11,23 $p < 0,02$ $p_1 < 0,05$	0,147±0,013 $p < 0,05$ $p_1 > 0,25$	0,80±0,06 $p < 0,02$ $p_1 < 0,05$
28 days	fracture	150,45±9,45 $p > 0,25$	0,174±0,015 $p > 0,3$	0,60±0,06 $p > 0,3$
	fire	158,86±12,10 $p > 0,1$ $p_1 > 0,6$	0,152±0,010 $p < 0,05$ $p_1 > 0,25$	0,54±0,03 $p > 0,7$ $p_1 > 0,4$

Table 2

Indicators of the state of bone tissue of the jaws of rats at different times after fracture or gunshot wound in the upper jaw

Periods	Groups	Bone alkaline phosphatase activity, $\mu\text{kat}/\text{kg}$	Elastase activity, $\mu\text{kat}/\text{kg}$	Alkaline phosphatase activity mcat/kg	Calcium content, mmol/g
Intact group		2,59±0,21	18,76±1,32	39,68±2,41	2,73±0,23
7 days	fracture	4,78±0,34 $p < 0,01$	26,66±1,14 $p < 0,01$	49,03±2,10 $p < 0,05$	2,23±0,20 $p > 0,1$
	fire	6,18±0,32 $p < 0,001$ $p_1 < 0,05$	40,75±1,84 $p < 0,001$ $p_1 < 0,002$	41,34±2,15 $p > 0,6$ $0,05 < p_1 < 0,1$	2,05±0,18 $0,05 < p < 0,1$ $p_1 > 0,5$
14 days	fracture	3,87±0,29 $p < 0,02$	24,08±1,00 $p < 0,05$	61,32±3,45 $p < 0,01$	2,39±0,26 $p > 0,3$
	fire	5,53±0,24 $p < 0,001$ $p_1 < 0,01$	36,34±1,12 $p < 0,001$ $p_1 < 0,001$	59,96±3,10 $p < 0,01$ $p_1 > 0,7$	2,15±0,21 $p > 0,1$ $p_1 > 0,5$
21 days	fracture	2,83±0,20 $p > 0,4$	21,28±1,10 $p > 0,2$	54,63±4,18 $p < 0,05$	2,84±2,84 $p > 0,69$
	fire	3,72±0,28 $p < 0,05$ $p_1 < 0,05$	25,09±1,40 $p < 0,05$ $0,05 < p_1 < 0,1$	65,08±3,94 $p < 0,01$ $p_1 > 0,1$	2,87±0,20 $p > 0,6$ $p_1 > 0,69$
28 days	fracture	2,71±0,21 $p > 0,7$	19,42±1,52 $p > 0,7$	43,08±3,26 $p > 0,4$	2,62±0,29 $p > 0,7$
	fire	2,88±0,22 $p > 0,4$ $p_1 > 0,6$	19,65±1,42 $p > 0,6$ $p_1 > 0,69$	55,11±3,36 $p < 0,02$ $p_1 < 0,05$	2,97±0,24 $p > 0,5$ $p_1 > 0,3$

Table 3

Indicators of the state of the mucous membrane of the oral cavity of rats at different times after fracture or gunshot wound in the upper jaw

Periods	Groups	Acid phosphatase activity, $\mu\text{kat}/\text{kg}$	Elastase activity, $\mu\text{kat}/\text{kg}$	Urease activity, $\mu\text{kat}/\text{kg}$	Catalase activity, μka	Malondialdehyde content mmol/kg
Intact group		19,68±1,24	52,67±3,12	0,626±0,024	9,68±0,42	8,01±0,68
7 days	fracture	22,06±1,10 $p > 0,2$	62,67±2,45 $0,05 < p < 0,1$	0,967±0,039 $p < 0,001$	5,05±0,23 $p < 0,001$	25,64±1,45 $p < 0,001$
	fire	34,29±1,27 $p < 0,001$ $p_1 < 0,001$	80,89±4,23 $p < 0,01$ $p_1 < 0,02$	1,257±0,067 $p < 0,001$ $p_1 < 0,02$	4,12±0,24 $p < 0,001$ $p_1 < 0,05$	19,07±1,12 $p < 0,001$ $p_1 < 0,02$
14 days	fracture	20,72±1,20 $p > 0,5$	61,73±3,12 $0,05 < p < 0,1$	0,910±0,045 $p < 0,01$	5,45±0,2 $p < 0,001$	15,87±0,93 $p < 0,001$
	fire	28,96±1,15 $p < 0,01$ $p_1 < 0,01$	72,34±3,12 $p < 0,01$ $0,05 < p_1 < 0,1$	1,080±0,056 $p < 0,001$ $0,05 < p_1 < 0,1$	4,10±0,32 $p < 0,001$ $p_1 < 0,02$	18,31±0,98 $p < 0,001$ $p_1 > 0,1$
21 days	fracture	18,32±1,12 $p > 0,4$	57,17±1,87 $p > 0,25$	0,760±0,034 $p < 0,05$	6,99±0,24 $p < 0,01$	10,34±0,76 $0,05 < p < 0,1$
	fire	23,62±1,12 $0,05 < p < 0,1$ $p_1 < 0,01$	67,17±2,76 $p < 0,02$ $p_1 < 0,05$	0,880±0,038 $p < 0,01$ $0,05 < p_1 < 0,1$	5,69±0,28 $p < 0,01$ $p_1 < 0,02$	12,86±0,84 $p < 0,01$ $0,05 < p_1 < 0,1$
28 days	fracture	17,26±1,32 $p > 0,2$	50,48±2,36 $p > 0,5$	0,750±0,028 $p < 0,02$	8,41±0,56 $p > 0,1$	8,97±0,63 $p > 0,3$
	fire	17,96±1,34 $p > 0,3$ $p_1 > 0,7$	64,13±3,10 $p < 0,05$ $p_1 < 0,02$	0,849±0,032 $p < 0,01$ $0,05 < p_1 < 0,1$	7,63±0,36 $p < 0,02$ $p_1 > 0,25$	9,63±0,67 $p > 0,1$ $p_1 > 0,5$

The analysis of the study results indicates that inflammation, contamination with opportunistic bacteria, activation of lipid peroxidation against the background of reduced antioxidant protection in the oral mucosa of rats after gunshot wounds were more intense than after a jaw fracture. After the gunshot wound at the last stage

in 28 days, the activity of elastase, urease and catalase in the oral mucosa of rats did not correspond to the normal level, i.e., signs of inflammation, bacterial contamination and a decrease in antioxidant defense in the oral cavity were preserved.

In the biochemical studies of pulp tissues on days

21 and 28 of the experiment, a significant increase in the level of acid phosphatase activity by 1.6 times ($p < 0.05$) and 1.5 times ($p < 0.02$) was observed in the pulp of the incisors of rats with gunshot wounds compared to the control group. At the same time, this index was increased by 45.4 % ($0.05 < p < 0.1$) after 21 days and by 44.2 % ($p < 0.05$) after 28 days of experiment compared to the corresponding index in group 1.

The activity of alkaline phosphatase in the pulp of rats' teeth after gunshot wounds on day 21 was significantly reduced by 34.4 % and 23.7 % ($p < 0.02-0.001$) on day 28 compared with the intact group. And in comparison with animals after jaw fracture, this index was lower by 26.9 % ($p < 0.02$) and 18.4 % ($p < 0.05$), respectively, on days 21 and 28 of injury. Accordingly, the index of pulp mineralization in rats as a ratio of alkaline phosphatase to acid phosphatase tended to decrease in relation to the control group after 21 days by 2.4 times ($0.05 < p < 0.1$), after 28 days – by 1.9 times ($p < 0.002$).

The analysis of the results of the pulp study indicates a violation of mineralization processes in rats with various types of jaw injuries. More significant pathological changes were recorded after gunshot wounds of the jaw: If at the last stage of observation the pulp indices of incisors in rats after jaw fracture corresponded to normal values in the intact group, then after gunshot wounds of the jaw the activity of destructive acid phosphatase was 1.5 times higher than normal and the index after fracture, and the activity of alkaline phosphatase and the pulp mineralization index were lower than normal values and the level of the corresponding indicators in rats after jaw fracture.

Histological examination revealed that the healing of both traumatic zones in both groups of animals was carried out according to the well-known laws of repair and regeneration, but the ratio of these processes was variable depending on the type of injury, the distribution of the injury zone, and the predominance of injury to a particular tissue. Reparative and regenerative processes within the same group of animals took place within identical timeframes and were morphologically identical. Various complicating factors in the form of secondary infection, additional effects of physical and chemical agents (gunpowder gases, powder masses and metal shavings in the wound) significantly deformed the course of healing processes. Soft tissue healing in both groups of animals proceeded with the formation of connective tissue (scar). But in group 2 (gunshot wound) it took longer. The healing of bone tissue in group 1 was mainly due to the proliferation of cartilaginous histone with subsequent ossification. Healing in

group 2 was mainly due to the growth of connective tissue with a variable degree of further ossification or without it at all with the formation of a false joint type structure. A variable ratio of these two processes was observed in both groups.

Conclusions. Thus, the studies show that the reparative processes in gunshot and non-gunshot wounds of the maxillofacial area follow the well-known laws of repair and regeneration with adequate antibiotic therapy. Indicators of the activity of inflammatory markers, primarily elastase, can be used as a diagnostic sign in planning the timing and scope of surgical and reconstructive operations and in the prevention of postoperative complications.

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